

MENTAL HEALTH STATUS OF YOUTH ORPHANS IN G20 PERSPECTIVES

SANMAY DAS ¹ | PROF. (DR.) NIMAI CHAND MAITI ²

¹ RESEARCH SCHOLAR, SEACOM SKILLS UNIVERSITY, KENDRADANGAL, BIRBHUM, W.B.

² PROFESSOR, DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, SEACOM SKILLS UNIVERSITY, KENDRA DANGAL, BIRBHUM, W.B.

ABSTRACT:

G20 is very crucial for our future generation as the different nation builders already live their life full by building nation by using everything in full. Then the question arises What about of our future generation? Some conscious human beings from different nation get focus on the deteriorate situation of environment, economy, energy, health, technology and start discussion to restore all such to continue the progress of development. Today a child is born with a challenge to live or to survive in this adverse situation. If this adverse situation effects really on who get everything like parent, love, care, nutrition, society than what about them who did not get all such and they are none but the orphans. This study is to measure the mental health status of youth orphans as the orphans are already deprived and try to survive with full opportunity which we should provide them. The researcher used qualitative method for this study. Mental Health Battery by A.K.Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta (2005, 2013) was adapted as questionnaire and standardized as per requirement to measure the mental health status of orphan children. The major findings of the study are that the orphans have mental health issues though in orphanages run by govt. or self-initiated, they live a secured life but those orphans who are out of this network are going through an awful life and in major cases they lost in dooms. As the orphans have full right to live in this world so we should think about them in G20 discussion also.

KEYWORDS:

MENTAL HEALTH, YOUTH ORPHAN, G20.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

15th June 2026

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

16th June 2026

INTRODUCTION:

In this century we are deteriorating physically, mentally, emotionally, socially and above all environmentally. This scenario is actually a threat to the human beings as to survive. In this century as we used everything desperately and did not think about future. The little girl named Greta Thunberg from Sweden who raised her voice alone to the world leaders about the climate change and asked them what will be the future? When she was just thirteen, she addressed to the world by founding a movement known as "Fridays for Future" (also called School Strike for Climate) in 2018 where she alone sits with poster in front of the Swedish assembly on every Friday. In this way the world leaders think and take action by implementing sustainable development. G20 is an another initiative to implement sustainability and protect world for future generation. In this adverse situation we have mental health issues as because the changing situation where our life become more complex. To live with everything should makes us healthy life when the orphans did not get everything and deprived almost in every aspect. In this century one issue that makes us trouble worldwide is mental health. Beside our physical health, we should take care of our mental

health to live a stable life in every aspect. In Indian Civilization we were very much concern in this issue from the beginning. Though mental health issues would be possible to recover to an ordinary man with some efforts but what about the orphan?

World Health Organization (2011) defines "mental health as a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, copes with normal stresses of life, works productively and fruitfully and is able to make a contribution to his or her community." According to Hadfield (1950) - "Mental health is full and harmonious functioning of the whole personality."

In our daily life we confront different issues, challenges, problems, emotional blocking, social hindrances which make us disturb and puzzle to make decision and cope with the situation. Sometime we resolve the puzzle sometime not as per our mental, physical, emotional, social ability. The ability to meet or cope the situation with skills and handle the issues technically and positively make a good mentally healthy person.

This is all about the person who lives with all that a person

can get in his life but what about the mental condition of orphans who live in orphanages? Simply orphan means someone who has lost father or mother or both. They have to live alone in this world. Their life starts with a challenge of survive in adverse situation.

UNICEF defines an orphan as “any children under the age of 18 who has lost one or both parents to death.” So the question What about their life, their education, their emotions, their mental health, their shelter, their struggling for existence?

The normal human being getting everything in his life may be good food, shelter, clothes, education, opportunities, material things but don't have a good mental health. They could not manage or handle the stress, emotions, adverse situation, failure, complications, challenges, fear, anxiety and many others that makes them running to the Psychiatrist or Counsellor for stability and cope with all such things. If is this a situation of a normal human beings than how the orphans lived and handle all those thing?

An estimated 153 million children worldwide are orphans(UNICEF). In India 9,589 orphanages are working (The Ministry of Women and Child Development Report2016-17). Out of this 91% are non- governmental which means that only 9% of them receive support from Govt. It is too much vulnerable situation that only few orphans are staying at orphanage but most of them are frequently lived in street or engaged anywhere as a child labour.

Some reasons behind how an orphan is getting into orphanages are Poverty,Disrupted family, Death of parents, Migration for searching of work, Too much nuclear family, Natural hazards etc.

SOME CHARACTERISTICS OF A PERSON HAVING GOOD MENTAL HEALTH ARE:

1. Defining, nurturing and continuing personal connections that mentally satisfying.
2. Balancing a sense of empathy for other people.
3. Utilize and gratify in solitude.
4. The capability to maintain the demands of daily life and recover from setback.
5. Having a strong sense of disposition with the capability to enjoy life.
6. Desire to engage to the fullest extent in life getting through Significant reverence and strong bonding.
7. The positive attitude towards the changing expands and undergoes a variety of change in accordance to the life circumstance.

Actually G20 is a way to stable our future by thrifty use of energy and restoring health not only physically but mentally also. G20 is an initiative to reach the goal of sustainability which is very much require in this scenario. One crucial thing is that a positive think will come from a positive person that means a person having a good mental health can change the scenario by spreading positivity. Beside our normal human being, we should take care of

the physical and mental health of deprived one, the orphans. Orphans have equal contribution in economic, environmental, social, climate change, sustainability, health and many other aspects if they get or we provide them the opportunity.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE:

STUDIES IN ABOARD:

1. **M,Cherewick., Ronald E, Dahl.,S,Priyanka. et.al (2023)** has conducted a study of the risk and protective factors for mental health and wellbeing among adolescent orphan in Tanzania. This research has demonstrated the importance of understanding risk factors for mental health and wellbeing. The main purpose of this study was to examine risk factors and protective factors among adolescent orphans. Survey interview method has been taken for this study. Result suggest that strong protective factors is important factors to target in intervention programs aimed at supporting adolescent mental wellbeing.
2. **S, Harms., R, Kizza., et.al (2009)** had been studied the conception of mental health among Ugandan youth orphaned by AIDS. A qualitative study was conducted to describe the experience of orphan hood and its impact on mental health. Interviews were taken to the samples. The findings of this study suggest that Western scenario was different from African context. The orphaned youth experienced significant ongoing emotional difficulties after the death of their parents. Poor mental health was associated with loss of basic life necessities like food, education or shelter.

STUDIES IN INDIA:

1. **Khalid, Sanna(2018)** has undertaken the study of Self Esteem level of happiness, aggressiveness, and mental health among institutionalized and non- institutionalized orphans in Kashmir valley. This study aimed to assess and compare the level of self-esteem, aggression, happiness and mental health in the orphanage with those orphans living at home with their family members. The objective behind this research was to highlight the problems faced by these orphans residing orphanage devoid of parental love, care, support. This research has been conducted through quantitative method with structured questionnaires. The research has been found that there was much difference between the level of self-esteem, happiness and aggressiveness of those orphan who lived with their family or lived in orphanage.
2. **Paul, N., Paul, T. (2018)** has studied the role of emotional intelligence among adolescent orphans in socialization and scholastic behavior. The researcher investigated the relationship of emotional intelligence and academic behavior of

the orphan adolescent in India. The samples were the institutionalized orphan children in Cochin. The result states that respondents experience moderate levels of emotional intelligence which is reflected in their scholastic behavior and socialization.

Statement of the problem: As we are going through a dismal situation throughout the world by war, climate change, global warming, threat, pressure, depression and negativity, so we should take care of our physical and mental health with restoring environment. So the researcher took this problem "Mental Health Status of Youth Orphans in G20 Perspectives."

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- ✓ To find out the mental health status of youth orphan in different orphanages.
- ✓ To focus on the scenario of different mental health issues in G20 perspective.
- ✓ To emphasize on the requirements of the orphans in present adverse situation.

Research Question: When the people in this earth are puzzled to satisfy the growing requirements then what would be the future in context with environment, energy, health, society, economic and above all survival in this adverse situation. G20 or other intergovernmental forum are trying to restore, reconstruct and rehabilitate environment but who will take care of our mental health and specially the deprived one, the orphans. The youth orphans like other youth may contribute in different burning issues which we are confronting now a day. The number of orphans are increasing day by day because of irresponsible, inhuman, immoral and unnatural behaviour of us. So the research questions are

1. What is the mental health status of youth orphan in present scenario?
2. Is G20 really important and essential for restoring mental health of youth orphan?

DEFINITION OF THE TERM:

Mental Health – a person's condition with regard to their psychological and emotional wellbeing.

Youth Orphan – is a minor bereft through "death or disappearance of, abandonment or desertion by, or separation or loss from both parents of age group 14 -18.

G20-is an intergovernmental forum focused on economic, sustainability, health and environmental issues.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

1. The study is really important as the youth orphans are deprived in different aspects which would come into focus in this study.
2. This study focused on the mental health status of youth orphans which is really a matter of concern.
3. How the G20 agendas are associated with the issues especially on mental health of youth orphans are

significant in this study.

METHODOLOGY:

- a. **Research Methodology:** Qualitative method has been followed for this study.
- b. **Focused Group Discussion:** The youth orphans of age group 14-18 have been taken as a sample of different orphanage in Dakshin Dinajpur, Uttar Dinajpur and Maldah district in West Bengal.
- c. **Tool is Used:** Mental Health Battery by A.K.Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta(2005,2013) was adapted as questionnaire and standardized as per requirement to measure the mental health status of orphan children.

Major Findings of the Study: Major findings of the study are

1. According to the questionnaire the orphans are really concerned about adverse situation and ready to serve country and society and environment.
2. According to another question they answered that they are always ready to share everything with another which is a positive indication of good mental health and for good human being which is globally lacking now.
3. In next question, they answered that they want to become a good responsible citizen which is really impacted on the present situation turns them into global citizen.
4. The most negative thing that has been found that our attitude towards them. Actually as they are deprived from everything, so society did not accept them properly.
5. It has been found that somehow they demotivated and turned into the dooms.
6. They want higher education but lack of interest in continuing education is very much clear in this respect.
7. They answered that they want to take part and contribute like others in society in different aspect which is crucial in G20 perspective.
8. The orphans have good mental health which is really required in present scenario and should need a proper channel to restore it for future.
9. In next question, they answered that yes, they have their own vision and perspective towards our nation and global changes.
10. They confirmed that like others they are also aware the planetary situation, politics, social changes by watching news in orphanages.

SUGGESTIONS:

- ❖ More emphasis should be given to the upbringing of orphans and make them worth in future perspective.

- ❖ More participation of orphans is required in global perspective.
- ❖ We should take care and arrange motivation program for nourishing good mental health of orphans.
- ❖ We should make them aware about the global situation and give them opportunity to take part positively.
- ❖ Gradually, as the number is increasing, the orphans would take a crucial place in future and contribute for sustainable developments.

CONCLUSION:

Though the orphans are deprived from every angle but keep struggling to survive, so we should try to bring them in front. Actually many orphans have good intellect or other qualities which will be lost if we did not nourish. As a responsible citizen we should bring them in front like other normal human being because we may get a good result from them also. In G20 perspective when we are trying to sustain our future then we should hold the hands of orphan otherwise they will have lost.

REFERENCES

1. M,Cherewick, Ronald E, Dahl,S,Priyanka. et.al (2023) A Study Of The Risk And Protective Factors For Mental Health And Wellbeing Among Adolescent Orphan In Tanzania.
2. Paul, N., Paul, T.(2018).Understanding the Role of Emotional Intelligence among Adolescent in Orphan in Socialization and Scholastic Behavior. Corpus ID: 226298830.
3. Sanna,K.(2018).A Study ofSelf esteem Level of Happiness Aggressiveness and Mental Health among Institutionalized and NonInstitutionalized Orphans in Kashmir Valley. Aligarh Muslim University. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/4974073>
4. S, Harms., R, Kizza., et.al (2009) The Conception Of Mental Health Among Ugandan Youth Orphaned By AIDS.
5. World Health Organization. (2011). *Mental health: A state of well-being*, Retrieved from http://www.who.int/features/factfiles/mental_health/en/